

STRUCTURAL EVOLUTION OF C/C-SiC COMPOSITES THROUGH THE MAIN PRODUCTION STEPS ON THE LIQUID SILICON INFILTRATION (LSI) ROUTE

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SUMMARY: Carbon fiber reinforced carbon- and SiC-matrix composites can be made by different production methods and are displaying characteristic microstructures. This paper focuses on the analysis of structural aspects induced by the fabrication process of C/C-SiC composites fabricated by the Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) method which was developed by DLR (German Aerospace Research Establishment).

The LSI method consists in three main production steps (CFRP, C/C and C/C-SiC state) and the evolution of the composite's morphology and structure is traced through these production steps from the carbon fiber reinforced plastics (CFRP) state to the finally processed C/C-SiC composite. Conventional optical microscopy, EPMA, REM and TEM serve as tools to disclose the microstructural organization and elemental informations in order to understand their origins and the implications on the finally processed composite materials.

INTRODUCTION

Several methods are well suited to produce carbon fiber reinforced SiC-matrix composites. Examples are the chemical vapour infiltration (CVI), various Si-polymer pyrolysis routes with/without filler and the Liquid Silicon Infiltration (LSI) method [1] which is developed at DLR (German Aerospace Research Establishment). It is based on a C-polymer pyrolysis and subsequently followed by an infiltration of liquid silicon. Each of these methods offers merits for particular economical or technological requirements. The LSI-method as a one shot-near net shape fabrication process is a quick and economical alternative to the other processes for many technical applications in near future [2]. The upscaling from the laboratory to a technical scale proved feasible. A large number of high performance real parts as e.g. an intake ramp for hypersonic propulsion systems or brakes are produced by this way and confirm the high level of technological development of the LSI-method [3,4,5].

Starting from the raw components the material has to undergo several transformations before the product reaches the final C/C-SiC condition. The following discussion puts emphasis on the elucidation of structural changes which take place accompanied with the three main processing steps which are Carbon Fiber Reinforced Plastic (CFRP), Carbon/Carbon (C/C) and C-fiber reinforced ceramic state (C/C-SiC).

For tracing the structural changes a specialized sample preparation is applied adequate to handle the strong heterogeneity of the composites. Through all the material states this is a basic requirement for the optical microscopy, REM (Raster Electron Microscope), EPMA (Electron Probe Micro Analyser) and TEM (Transmission Electron Microscope) investigations. The sample's architecture is shown clearly by the optical microscopy. EPMA serves informations about elemental distributions within the C/C-SiC samples, whereas REM and imaging TEM disclose further details of the microstructural organization. This way the fiber/matrix interfaces, the reaction zones or even C-fiber damages are depicted.

THE LIQUID INFILTRATION METHOD

The LSI method [1,2,3] is a relatively fast fabrication process that consists of three processing steps, which are passed through just one time during the whole fabrication cycle (Fig. 1). Starting materials are stacks of 2D carbon fiber cloth (plain weave) and high carbon yield polymeric C-precursors which have to fulfill particular requirements induced by the processing.

1. CFRP forming (5-20bar, Polymerization, 200°C, inert atmosphere):

The first step of composite fabrication applies the Resin Transfer Moulding to inject the polymer into the stack of carbon fiber cloth. The subsequent polymerization is performed in a furnace applying a well defined time-temperature profile. It is accompanied with development of little matrix porosity but significant matrix shrinkage which causes a periodic primary segmentation within the fiber bundles.

2. C/C forming (Pyrolysis, 1 bar, N₂, 900°C):

The CRFP composite undergoes a thermolysis with well controlled time-temperature profile during the next fabrication step. A great matrix volume shrinkage is accompanied by substantial structural changes. A multiply connected translaminar channel system and a second segmentation of fiber bundles is formed. The characteristic micro crack pattern depends essentially on the fiber matrix binding strength.

3. C/C-SiC forming (Liquid Silicon infiltration, vacuum, 1550°C):

Capillary forces are the driving forces of the infiltration of liquid elemental Si into the C/C channel system under vacuum conditions, after preheating the C/C composite. The accompanied diffusion controlled reaction between carbon and silicon is strongly dependent on the pore size distribution of the infiltrated C/C-composite but also on the particular modification of carbon being present within the reaction zone. The time-temperature profile is very essential for tailoring the desired product properties. Fig. 1 schematically displays such a profile ("Brennkurve") [3].

Fig. 1: Schematic Time-Temperature Profile (‘Brennkurve’) of the LSI process [3]

EXPERIMENTAL

All samples independently whether CFRP, C/C or C/C-SiC state are cut from plate like composites using a diamond saw under well defined angles with the laminate layers. The ceramographical preparation makes use of supporting rings inserted into the conductive embedding material. Grinding applies various SiC papers down to 14 μm grain size. Polishing on cotton cloth using OP-S suspensions (0,25 μm grain size) follows subsequently. To prevent electron induced matrix degradation of CFRP samples a gold coating is applied and REM is operated in such cases at low voltages (<5kV). The TEM preparation additionally required dimple grinding (diamond paste of 3 μm) and subsequent conventional ion milling (PIPS).

RESULTS

CFRP State

The CFRP real structure (Fig. 2a,b) results from the matrix shrinkage and superimposed shrinkage impediment along the C-fiber axes. An almost periodic division of the fiber bundles in small segments is seen. Preparation of samples parallel to the laminate layers discloses the existence of two perpendicular crack systems which are almost independent of each other (Fig. 2b). The polymerisation and degassing conditions (one parameter e.g. is the pressure) as well as the type of raw materials exercise a strong influence on the development of open and closed porosity within matrix rich areas and inside the fiber bundles.

The matrix rich areas usually display a homogeneously dispersed closed porosity. A careful mechanical sample preparation partially retains an additional foamy phase located at crack sites (Fig. 3a) or independent of cracks (Fig. 3b).

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2: Optical micrograph of CFRP composite: a) perpendicular b) parallel to laminate layer

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3: REM micrograph of foamy matrix (CFRP) a) adjacent to crack b) independent of crack

(a)

(b)

Fig.4: C/C state sample (a) overview (b) foamy matrix component

C/C State

The applied pyrolysis induces very severe structural changes to the CFRP-composite caused by the mass loss (60% carbon yield) during pyrolysis (Fig. 4a). A multiply connected open channel system develops and the closed porosity in bulk matrix areas grows significantly.

The increased crack width in matrix rich areas is evident as well as the periodical occurrence of regions within the fiber bundles where the average distance between neighbouring fibers increased (zone of reduced fiber density). This periodicity corresponds to that of the primary segmentation as observed in the CFRP-state. To some extent a fiber rearrangement takes place (larger fiber distance) in areas of primary segmentation but also a displacement of a foamy matrix component into the bulk matrix cracks is observed (Fig. 4b). The foamy matrix component usually is separated from bulky matrix or fibers by very fine cracks (Fig.4a). Additionally a second segmentation takes place within the C-fiber bundles but these cracks are not filled by any foamy matrix component. Polarized light microscopy which is performed additionally gives indications that stress induced graphite is formed locally within the fiber bundles even at processing temperature as low as 900°C.

C/C-SiC State

A characteristic of C/C-SiC is the segmented wall structure which develops from the open channel system of the C/C state by the infiltration of liquid silicon (Fig. 5a). This channel system extends over large distances and is shown most clearly if the cut section is in parallel to the laminate layers (Fig. 5b). The infiltration and the accompanied chemical reaction shows a locally different behaviour (Fig. 6a) which is dependent not only of the width of the pores but also correlated to the carbon modifications reacting with Si and their lateral distribution within the reaction zone. C-matrix modifications of different appearance were detected in the C/C state. After the infiltration the former crack areas still can be identified in large scale by optical microscopy. Their structure reflects the former course of reaction between Silicon and Carbon. The REM investigations of C/C-SiC materials require a gold coating in order to prevent charging but clearly reveal topographical inequalities at higher magnifications. They originate in the different hardness of the substrate's surface and become effective during the mechanical sample preparation (Fig.6b). The reaction zones mostly display a cloud like shape and consist of a brittle material (Fig. 7a) which is retained only under dedicated sample preparation. The reaction between silicon and carbon involves both fiber and matrix. Even submicrometric pores are efficiently infiltrated.

A typical crack area which generated from a zone of reduced fiber density by Si infiltration (Fig. 6b) shows sharp topographical steps in central areas and a less sharp and brittle type adjacent to the carbon fiber bundles or to bulky matrix areas as displayed in Fig. 7a under higher magnification. The gold coating, and the limited accuracy of conventional EDS (Energy Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy) equipment for the detection of light elements, as carbon, give a preference to WDS (Wavelength Dispersive X-ray Spectroscopy) EPMA investigations of the elemental distribution. Since no sample charging was observed, no gold coating had to be applied. The Si elemental maps (as Fig.7b) and topographical images show some general features as pure Si areas (white) embedded in Si-rich areas of large grain size (central grey), Si-supply channels (dark grey) and fine grained areas (grey) with concentration gradients. They are adjacent to the unreacted carbon zones (dark black). Transmission electron micrographs usually show that even narrow infiltrated pores consist in a core of coarse grained SiC at almost the same position as the former pore and a reaction zone consisting of

fine grained SiC surrounding it (Fig. 8a). Elemental Si also can be detected locally but preferentially within the wide “pores”. The fine grained SiC area occasionally displays microcracks ending at closed porosity. Closed porosity in the C/C state preferentially accumulates near fiber surfaces (Fig. 8b) and modifies the resulting fiber matrix binding strength. The closed C/C state porosity usually is retained during the silicon infiltration leading to voids in the C/C-SiC reaction zones. TEM imaging proves that even submicrometric cracks which are connected to the open channel system are infiltrated efficiently. Their reaction zones have the same characteristic appearance as the larger ones. Another interesting observation can be made in front of the reaction zones inside the carbon fibers. Analogous effects were found in the carbon matrix (Fig 8a), too. The fibers show indications of damages within a range of several hundred nanometers in front of the reaction zone in apparently unreacted areas of the fibers. Whereas the segregations in the fibers seem oriented along the fiber axis, the segregations in the matrix appear in a more spherical shape.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 5: Segmented wall structure of C/C-SiC a) perpendicular b) parallel to laminate layers

(a)

(b)

Fig. 6: C/C-SiC reaction zones (a) optical micrograph (b) REM micrograph

(a) (b)
 Fig. 7: C/C-SiC (a) reaction zone (REM) (b) Si-elemental map (EPMA-WDS)

(a) (b)
 Fig. 8: C/C-SiC (a) crack structure (TEM) (b) accumulated closed porosity (TEM)

DISCUSSION

It is likely that the WDS Si-elemental map (Fig. 7b) is taken from an area which before the Si infiltration took place resembled that of Fig. 4b but showed additional open porosity. The narrow cracks separating the foamy matrix from the regular composite are assumed to be connected with the open porosity. Under this condition liquid silicon is supplied by the the open pores and distributed to the narrower cracks. The higher Si concentration compared to other crack areas can be explained by this argument. The foamy matrix in central parts of the zone of reduced fiber density serves as easily accessible carbon reservoir for the Si-C reaction. Due to the direct impregnation of the foamy matrix by liquid silicon the diffusion distances are short and the course of reaction is much more advanced compared to those regions where the reaction is based on the long distance diffusion of the reaction partners. Finally in such areas a recrystallization can take place and form large crystallites, as seen by TEM micrographs (Fig. 8a) or less pronounced in mass contrast or topo images. The hardest component is the coarse grained phase (SiC), whereas the weakest is elemental silicon. The correlated topographical steps can be detected on suitably prepared samples. Only pores

which are directly infiltrated can be filled up by this method; closed porosity will remain closed porosity, independent of whether the carbon of the surrounding reacts to SiC or not. As a hypothesis, the segregations within the fibers in front of the reaction zone may grow due to a Si gas phase infiltration inside the nanoporosity of the fiber.

A suitable segmentation and pore size distribution is essential for good infiltration results. The fiber-matrix binding strength is one of the controlling parameters of the segmentation width. Hardening during CFRP forming is accompanied with a matrix shrinkage and a first segmentation of the fiber bundles inside the 2D (0°-90°) CFRP composite. Subsequent pyrolysis causes further shrinkage and an additional segmentation. Wanner [6] created a model to describe the periodicity of this secondary segmentation based on the internal stress distribution of the composite.

The controlled release of gaseous reaction products has to take place in order to reduce the size of bubbles and not to accumulate too much closed porosity inside the composite. The corresponding time-temperature profiles (“Brennkurve”) are tailored for each precursor and based on thermogravimetric and thermoanalytical investigations.

CONCLUSIONS

Tracing the structure of the starting CFRP-material through the subsequent manufacturing steps (Pyrolysis and Si infiltration) the foamy matrix component leads to coarse grained SiC areas when infiltrated directly. If not infiltrated directly this porosity is conserved as an area of weak binding. The importance of an effective control of crack size and porosity during C/C-SiC fabrication is confirmed.

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